

**THE FOCUS ON PEOPLE AND QUALITY EDUCATION IS CRUCIAL FOR
ADDRESSING THE ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL CHALLENGES OF THE COUNTRY'S
DEVELOPMENT IN THE YEAR AHEAD**

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Abstract. *In this article, in the year of quality education in our country, attention will be paid not only to people, but also to economic and social issues that led to the development and modernization of our country. Mainly ways to improve the quality of education modern approaches are described.*

Keywords: *modernization, pedagogical technologies, quality of education, professional knowledge.*

INTRODUCTION

During the past period, within the framework of the Action Strategy on the five priority directions of the development of our country in 2017-2021, about 300 laws and more than 4,000 decisions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan aimed at the fundamental reform of all spheres of state and social life were adopted. Also, systematic work was carried out to ensure human rights, strengthen the accountability and openness of state bodies, and increase the role of civil society institutions, mass media, and the political activity of population and public associations. By the Decree of the President of February 28, 2023, the state program for the implementation of the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for the period of 2022-2026 in the "Year of human attention and quality education" was approved.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY.

The aim is to improve the standard of living for the population, align education with international standards, promote economic stability and growth, and reduce poverty. This is in line with the objectives set out in the New Uzbekistan Development Strategy for 2022-2026 and the President's Address to the Oliy Majlis and the People of Uzbekistan. The goal is to take the ongoing reforms to the next level.

❖ The state program for the implementation of the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 in the "year of attention to people and quality education" (hereinafter — State program) should be approved in accordance with the appendix.

The Cabinet of Ministers, the Council of Ministers of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, the governors of the regions and the city of Tashkent should organize the implementation of the State program on the basis of effective and strict discipline and determine practical measures in each district, city and neighborhood within 10 days, and the general public and regularly listen to the reports of the responsible persons in the presence of mass media.

Chambers of the Oliy Majlis and local councils should be advised to study the implementation of the State program in districts, cities and neighborhoods, and to listen to the reports of the heads of the responsible state bodies.

In order to improve the quality of education and reform the industry based on advanced foreign experience:

- From September 1, 2023, the practice of teaching students two foreign languages and one profession in one general secondary educational institution of each district (city) will be gradually launched;

- Starting from the 2023/2024 academic year, the following will be put into practice:

- teaching students in the 1st-4th grades of general secondary educational institutions according to the textbooks developed on the basis of advanced foreign experience;

- to provide students with basic knowledge of general education subjects in grades 5-9;

- Providing knowledge based on specialized programs that match the interests and abilities of 10-11th grade students.

Starting from the 2023/2024 academic year, primary school students will be provided with free meals in all regions of the republic and in the city of Tashkent.

Starting from the 2023/2024 academic year, state grants will be allocated to colleges and technical schools for dual education.

From April 1, 2023:

- the basic tariff rates of pedagogues of professional educational institutions correspond to the basic tariff rates of pedagogues of general secondary educational institutions;

- teacher of the first and second qualification category of a general secondary educational institution according to the basic tariff rates of the professional educational institution with the first and second qualification category, higher education without qualification category and industrial education masters without higher education, is equal to the basic tariff rates of a teacher with a higher education and a teacher with a secondary special education.

DISCUSSION.

The economic and social issues in Uzbekistan's development that are being addressed through the focus on "Attention to people and quality education" may include factors such as poverty reduction, improving the standard of living for the population, aligning education with international standards, promoting economic stability and growth, and addressing other social issues such as healthcare, infrastructure, and employment opportunities. Several factors may have influenced the decision to focus on "Attention to people and quality education" in Uzbekistan to address economic and social issues in the country's development. These factors may include:

1. Demographic changes: Uzbekistan has a young population, and investing in quality education can help to prepare the younger generation for the future workforce and improve their economic prospects.

2. Economic challenges: Uzbekistan has faced economic challenges in recent years, including high unemployment rates and low economic growth. Improving the quality of education can help to address these challenges by providing the workforce with the skills and knowledge needed to drive economic growth.

3. Globalization: As the world becomes more interconnected, it is increasingly important for Uzbekistan to align its education system with international standards to remain competitive in the global economy.

4. Social issues: Uzbekistan faces several social issues, including poverty, healthcare, and infrastructure. Improving the quality of education can help to address these issues by providing

individuals with the skills and knowledge needed to improve their economic prospects and contribute to society.

5. The need to improve the quality of education in Uzbekistan to meet international standards and prepare the workforce for the demands of a modern economy.

6. The desire to reduce poverty and improve the standard of living for the population by promoting economic growth and stability.

7. The recognition that investing in education and human capital is essential for long-term economic development.

8. The need to address social issues such as inequality, unemployment, and access to healthcare.

9. The desire to promote social cohesion and national unity by providing equal opportunities for all citizens to access quality education and participate in the country's development.

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